

The Influence of Training, Compensation, and Career Development on Employee Job Satisfaction and Sustainable Employee Performance at Prolindo Group Companies

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Abstract: The purpose of this research is to identify and explain the effect of training, compensation, and career development on sustainable employee performance, with employee job satisfaction as a mediating variable (case study: Prolindo Group). This research is a quantitative study of 103 Prolindo Group employees. The sampling technique is non-probability sampling where the sample is 103 permanent employees. The sources are primary and secondary data. The data analysis method used by SEM-PLS with SmartPLS version 3.2.9 software. The results of the study show that: (1) Training, compensation, and career development partially have a positive and significant effect on sustainable employee performance with a contribution of 71.60%; (2) Partially, employee job satisfaction has no effect and is not significant on sustainable employee performance; (3) Training and career development partially have a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction with a contribution of 73.20%; (4) Partial compensation has no effect and is not significant on employee job satisfaction; and (5) Employee job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect in mediating training, compensation and career development on sustainable employee performance. 20%; (4) Partial compensation has no effect and is not significant on employee job satisfaction; and (5) Employee job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect in mediating training, compensation, and career development on sustainable employee performance. 20%; (4) Partial compensation has no effect and is not significant on employee job satisfaction; and (5) Employee job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect in mediating training, compensation, and career development on sustainable employee performance.

Keywords:- Training, Compensation, Career Development, Employee Job Satisfaction, Sustainable Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization, all companies are required to continue to innovate to achieve a competitive advantage.

One of the things the company can do is manage human resources effectively and efficiently. HR is an important asset for a company that must be managed properly to create company goals. For this reason, the company expects all employees to show their best performance.

Human resources are the only resources that have feelings, skills, desires, encouragement, knowledge, energy, and work (Ahn & Huang, 2020).

Human resources have an impact on the company's efforts to achieve company goals. Apart from providing adequate capital and materials, it is difficult for an organization to achieve its goals without human resources. People are the main investment in any organization; therefore, it must be managed accordingly (Bush, 2020).

Sustainable employee performance is the result of work performed by employees, which is related to the duties and responsibilities given by the company about the goals and performance of its employees. High-performing employees are certainly one of the company's strengths and advantages. Employee performance certainly does not come by itself, many factors affect employee performance such as salary, facilities, and career. Of course, if these factors are sufficient, employees will do their best in terms of productivity. Prolindo Group is currently in a situation where the performance of its employees is declining, which has an impact on the company's production process and is not optimal. Salary is the remuneration paid by company employees for their work. In this case, it cannot be denied that employee performance is more or less related to compensation. When the compensation offered by the company is sufficient, employees feel happy, and productivity increases.

In this case, Prolindo Group as a company engaged in the oil and gas sector should have employees who work with enthusiasm and satisfaction, and carry out their work effectively and efficiently, so that in the end they show high productivity in following their vision. has been fixed. Thus employee job satisfaction is a very important issue in a company because it can increase employee work productivity. Therefore, management's ability to provide

employee job satisfaction is a factor that determines the sustainability of the company. Understanding the importance of employee job satisfaction in improving sustainable employee performance.

Prolindo Group's performance can be seen from its performance achievements in the 2019-2021 period.

Table 1 Results of Employee Performance HRD Data

No	Year	Mark Average	Target Value
1	2019	79,89	85
2	2020	75.35	85
3	2021	76.00	85

Source: Prolindo Group (2022)

From Table 1 it is very clear that the achievement of employee performance scores is not ideal, it can be seen from the average score that no one achieves elite results. Then based on the above it can be seen that the performance of employees at Prolindo Group has not met the targets set. This shows that the achievement of the satisfaction index is not yet optimal as a reflection of employee performance that is not optimal. Therefore, a qualified workforce is an

absolute necessity for companies in achieving maximum service to customers. Thus it is necessary to evaluate the factors that influence sustainable employee performance to achieve the company's wishes.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that the results of the pre-survey of problems regarding employee performance are in the form of a table as follows:

Table 2 Results of the Sustainable Employee Performance Pre-Survey

No	Variable	Behavior Indicators	Results		Percentage (%)	
			Yes	No	Yes	No
1	Sustainable Employee Performance	1 I work according to the Standard Operating Procedure and can fulfill the Key Performance Indicators that have been made.	7	8	46,67	73,33
		2 I always work well and correctly and there are no problems related to work and the social environment of work.	7	8	46,67	80.00
		3 I always communicate with my superiors about the work I do.	6	9	40.00	53,33
Average			6,67	8.33	44,44	55,56

Source: September 2022 Pre-Survey

The organization measures sustainable employee performance by monitoring the performance of the economy, society, and environment in parallel. Sustainable performance measures and assesses the company's performance from all aspects and for all stakeholders. Since organizations consider both upstream and downstream stakeholders when measuring sustainable performance, there are no boundary conditions in this arena (Charter & Tischner, 2017). In the same context, Burawat (2019) claims that sustainable organizations focus on using minimum resources, reducing gas emissions, promoting environmental initiatives, and creating value for various stakeholders, along with improving their financial performance. Furthermore, as a sustainable leader consider the long-term aspect.

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In an increasingly stressful business environment, both locally and globally, many companies today are trying to find innovative reward strategies that are directly related to company improvement. This encourages a paradigm shift in the modern company. This condition must be implemented and prepared proportionally. This preparation is primarily based on highly qualified employees with appropriate conditions.

Table 3 Pre-Survey Results of Variables X1, X2, X3 & Y1

No	Variable	Behavior Indicators	Results		Percentage (%)		
			Yes	No	Yes	No	
1 11	Training	1	Training materials are provided according to job requirements.	4	11	26,67	73,33
		2	The level of accuracy of the training method used with the delivery of the material.	3	12	20,00	80,00
		3	The skills and abilities possessed by employees are by the work given.	7	8	46,67	53,33
		Average		4,67	10,33	31,11	68,89
22	Compensation	4	I received a salary increase based on my work performance and responsibility towards work.	4	11	26,67	73,33
		5	I get family benefits beyond the minimum wage.	5	10	33,33	66,67
		6	I get an incentive allowance if I meet the set targets.	3	12	20,00	80,00
		Average		4,00	11,00	26,67	73,33
33	Career Development	7	Does career policy affect the performance of employees in the company?	7	8	46,67	53,33
		8	Are you satisfied with the career program that has been held by the company?	5	10	33,33	66,67
		9	With the recruitment of PKWT to become PKWTT, can this create opportunities for employees to reach a higher career path?	6	9	40,00	60,00
		Average		6,00	9,00	40,00	60,00
44	Employee Job Satisfaction	10	Do the people I work with provide me with sufficient support?	6	9	40,00	60,00
		11	Am I satisfied with my friends here?	4	11	26,67	73,33
		12	Do I work with responsible people?	6	9	40,00	60,00
		Average		5,33	9,67	35,56	64,44

Source: September 2022 Pre-Survey

Based on Table 3 above, it can be seen that the results of the pre-survey (questionnaire) state that each X variable, namely training, compensation, and career development, is still not optimally carried out by Prolindo Group employees, where the average percentage of the pre-survey results for each X variable is 68, 89%; 73.33% and 60.00%. Likewise for the Y variable, namely employee job satisfaction and sustainable employee performance, it is still not optimally run with the average percentage of each Y variable being 64.44% and 55.56%.

Some of the identification of problems that arise in companies include: 1) Job training at Prolindo Group, employees during job training still do not understand the material conveyed by the speaker. 2) Employees have not received incentives and bonuses if the targets set are achieved otherwise if employees do not reach the targets set then employees do not get incentives and bonuses. 3) Career Planning is unclear, making it difficult to get a career position. 4) There is still a lack of opportunities and rewards from the company as indicated by employee dissatisfaction. 5) The performance of Prolindo Group employees is still not optimal. Given the gap phenomenon above, the authors are interested in conducting research at the Prolindo Group entitled "The Influence of Training,

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW

➤ Training

Rivai, Veithzal, and Basri in Andianto and Sugiyanto (2019) explain that training is a personal (generally one-to-one), on-the-job approach used by managers and trainers to help develop their level of skills and abilities. Wayne and Mondy in Adiyanto and Sugiyanto (2019) explain that the purpose of this training is to equip students with the knowledge and skills they need for their current jobs. Gomes in Nursalim and Sulastrri (2020).

➤ Compensation

Salary is a component of labor relations that often creates problems in labor market relations. Salary issues have always been a concern of management, staff, and organizational government, especially salaries (Sundari et al., 2020). Wages are considered by management because they constitute a large part of the production and operating costs, determine the performance that employees must pay, and affect their ability to hire workers of a certain quality.

➤ Career Development

Career development is the advancement of one's position in an organization to the highest position one has achieved in their working life. The importance of career development in companies increases loyalty, creativity, and employee satisfaction. Measures of employee career development include promotions, potential skills, responsibilities, awards, and qualifications (Busro, 2018).

➤ *Employee Job Satisfaction Employees*

Job satisfaction is one of the variables that influence work performance or employee productivity, along with motivation, stress levels, physical working conditions, salary, and other financial, technical, and behavioral aspects. Productivity can be increased by increasing job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is the result of productivity or vice versa. High productivity only leads to increased job satisfaction when employees feel that their performance (salary/salary) is fair and reasonable and is linked to excellent job performance. In other words, it shows the level of employee satisfaction with work performance, because the company can know the level aspects. (Setyo, 2017).

➤ *Sustainable Employee Performance*

According to Edison et al. (2020: 203) explains: "Performance is the result of a process related to certain conditions or agreements and is measured against them over a certain period." In addition, Busro (2020: 99) explains: "Efficiency is the result of work done in terms of quality and quantity of work and can be explained according to one's role in an organization or business. This includes skills,

abilities, and abilities in carrying out work. Based on the description above, it can be explained that the performance of an employee is the result of high-quality work carried out within a certain period and in quantity, skill, ability, and knowledge.

➤ *Previous Research*

Taufan Andri R, Effy Yuswita, and Novi Haryati (2021) in his research stated that employee job training is positive and significant to performance. Sari Dewi Oktari, and Agatha Rinta Suhardi (2021) in their research there is an influence between compensation on employee performance. Muhammad Dedi Syahputra & Hasrudy Tanjung (2020) in their research career development has a significant influence on employee performance. Then Yohana Latifah, Muafi Muafi (2021) in her research Job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance.

➤ *Research Framework*

Based on all explanations of the relationship between variables, the framework in this study is presented in the following figure:

Fig 1 Thinking Framework

III. METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is a quantitative research method with a descriptive approach. This study uses primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data from the Prolindo Group. The population referred to in this study is the Prolindo Group of 103 employees.

The data analysis method used in this study is multiple linear regression analysis using SmartPLS version 3.2.9. While the test consists of 1) Testing the measurement model (Outer Model), 2) Testing the structural model (Inner Model) and 3) Testing the hypothesis.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Measurement Model Test (Outer Model)

The results of the calculation of the measurement model for all indicators for each variable in this study have met the requirements for a loading factor value ≥ 0.5 as can be seen in the following table:

Table 4 Outer Loading Test Results for Sustainable Employee Performance

Variable		Dimensions	Indicator	loading	Condition	Results
Training (X1)	1.1	Objective	P1.1	0.871	> 0.5	Valid
			P 1.2	0.889	> 0.5	Valid
	1.2	Trainers	P 2.1	0.831	> 0.5	Valid
			P 2.2	0.885	> 0.5	Valid
			P 2.3	0.771	> 0.5	Valid
	1.3	Training materials	P 3.1	0.918	> 0.5	Valid
			P 3.2	0.915	> 0.5	Valid
	1.4	Training Methods	P 4.1	0.879	> 0.5	Valid
			P 4.2	0.818	> 0.5	Valid
	1.5	Training Participants	P 5.1	0.824	> 0.5	Valid
P 5.2			0.901	> 0.5	Valid	
Compensation (X2)	2.1	Salary and Wages	K 1.1	0.890	> 0.5	Valid
			K 1.2	0.837	> 0.5	Valid
	2.2	Incentive	K 2.1	0.802	> 0.5	Valid
			K 2.2	0.884	> 0.5	Valid
	2.3	Allowances	K 3.1	0.875	> 0.5	Valid
			K 3.2	0.802	> 0.5	Valid
	2.4	Facility	K 4.1	0.917	> 0.5	Valid
			K 4.2	0.916	> 0.5	Valid
Career Development (X3)	3.1	Career Clarity	PK 1.1	0.929	> 0.5	Valid
			PK 1.2	0.912	> 0.5	Valid
	3.2	Self-development	PK 2.1	0.811	> 0.5	Valid
			PK 2.2	0.818	> 0.5	Valid
			PK 2.3	0.889	> 0.5	Valid
			PK 2.4	0.879	> 0.5	Valid
3.3	Work Quality Improvement	PK 3.1	0.945	> 0.5	Valid	
		PK 3.2	0.936	> 0.5	Valid	
Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	4.1	Wages	KKK_1.1	0.909	> 0.5	Valid
			KKK_1.2	0.931	> 0.5	Valid
			KKK_1.3	0.920	> 0.5	Valid
	4.2	Promotion	KKK_2.1	0.871	> 0.5	Valid
			KKK_2.2	0.875	> 0.5	Valid
			KKK_2.3	0.732	> 0.5	Valid
	4.3	Working Conditions	KKK_3.1	0.929	> 0.5	Valid
KKK_3.2			0.919	> 0.5	Valid	
Sustainable employee performance (Y2)	5.1	Contextual Performance	KKB_1.1	0.789	> 0.5	Valid
			KKB_1.2	0.817	> 0.5	Valid
			KKB_1.3	0.809	> 0.5	Valid
			KKB_1.4	0.796	> 0.5	Valid
	5.2	Adaptive Performance	KKB_2.1	0.894	> 0.5	Valid
			KKB_2.2	0.878	> 0.5	Valid
			KKB_2.3	0.897	> 0.5	Valid

➤ *Convergent Validity with Average Variance Extracted (AVE)*

The results of examining the AVE value in this test have met the requirements for an AVE value ≥ 0.5 as can be seen in Table 5

Table 5 Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Value

Variable	Average Variance Extracted(AVE)	Condition	Results
Training (X1)	0.553	> 0.5	Valid
Compensation (X2)	0.522	> 0.5	Valid

Career Development (X3)	0.693	> 0.5	Valid
Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.642	> 0.5	Valid
Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.590	> 0.5	Valid

➤ *Discriminant Validity*

Discriminant Validity testing is carried out to find out whether an indicator used is correctly and well reflective for measuring its construct based on the principle that each indicator has a greater value than the value of one indicator against another indicator (Ghozali & Latan, 2021). There are two ways to test discriminant validity using SmartPLS, the first way is to look at the cross-loading value of each indicator and the second way is to look at the Fornell-Lecker value.

➤ *Discriminant Validity with Cross Loading*

The cross-loading score is determined by comparing the magnitude of the relationship between each indicator and the variables. To get valid results, the relationship between each dimension and the variable must be greater than the relationship between each dimension and the other variables, as shown in Table 6 (numbers in bold). From this, it can be concluded that discriminant validity is met because it predicts better the indicators of this variable than indicators of other latent variables.

Table 6 Cross Loading Each Research Indicator and Variable

Indicator	Training (X1)	Compensation (X2)	Development Career (X3)	Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)
P_1.1	0.699	0.361	0.496	0.429	0.531
P_1.2	0.759	0.452	0.541	0.517	0.630
P_2.1	0.771	0.386	0.534	0.468	0.592
P_2.2	0.829	0.466	0.567	0.509	0.656
P_2.3	0.697	0.541	0.522	0.500	0.474
P_3.1	0.824	0.599	0.611	0.694	0.677
P_3.2	0.812	0.487	0.561	0.613	0.647
P_4.1	0.752	0.364	0.445	0.479	0.535
P_4.2	0.623	0.264	0.323	0.375	0.485
P_5.1	0.596	0.294	0.402	0.435	0.470
P_5.2	0.780	0.475	0.609	0.622	0.638
K_1.1	0.467	0.762	0.611	0.507	0.409
K_1.2	0.476	0.720	0.579	0.649	0.559
K_2.2	0.398	0.721	0.597	0.567	0.463
K_3.1	0.464	0.637	0.477	0.494	0.423
K_4.1	0.342	0.741	0.646	0.529	0.321
K_4.2	0.375	0.746	0.639	0.549	0.431
PK_1.1	0.418	0.774	0.824	0.686	0.470
PK_1.2	0.470	0.706	0.758	0.701	0.524
PK_2.1	0.690	0.568	0.801	0.715	0.632
PK_2.2	0.470	0.543	0.748	0.534	0.517
PK_2.3	0.559	0.722	0.878	0.661	0.567
PK_2.4	0.623	0.687	0.857	0.675	0.652
PK_3.1	0.660	0.732	0.920	0.735	0.745
PK_3.2	0.676	0.726	0.857	0.726	0.691
KKK_1.1	0.598	0.643	0.675	0.819	0.581
KKK_1.2	0.520	0.647	0.661	0.870	0.618
KKK_1.3	0.533	0.605	0.594	0.834	0.560
KKK_2.1	0.504	0.581	0.668	0.754	0.558
KKK_2.2	0.565	0.663	0.726	0.856	0.688
KKK_2.3	0.499	0.553	0.565	0.613	0.561
KKK_3.1	0.607	0.527	0.649	0.836	0.641
KKK_3.2	0.642	0.676	0.692	0.797	0.697
KKB_1.1	0.506	0.582	0.614	0.628	0.712
KKB_1.2	0.465	0.470	0.476	0.531	0.710
KKB_1.3	0.589	0.494	0.516	0.602	0.761
KKB_1.4	0.669	0.555	0.675	0.625	0.805
KKB_2.1	0.671	0.402	0.547	0.611	0.834
KKB_2.2	0.647	0.396	0.546	0.589	0.786
KKB_2.3	0.684	0.439	0.588	0.612	0.838

➤ *Discriminant Validity with Fornell-Lecker*

The Fornell-Larcker criterion method is a measurement method that proposes to compare the square root value of the extracted average variance (AVE) of each latent variable with the correlation between other latent variables in the model. If the AVE square root of each variable is greater than the correlation value between one variable and the other variables, then the model is said to have good discriminant validity (Fornell and Larker, 1981 in Hair, Tomas, Ringle, Sarstedt, Danks, & Ray, 2021).

Table 7 Fornell-Larcker Value

Variable	X1	X2	X3	Y1	Y2	Information
Training (X1)	0.831					Valid
Compensation (X2)	0.751	0.779				Valid
Career Development (X3)	0.740	0.594	0.749			Valid
Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.684	0.776	0.566	0.777		Valid
Employee performance Sustainable (Y2)	0.805	0.729	0.818	0.702	0.832	Valid

Based on Table 7 it is found that the AVE root value of each variable with the variable itself is greater than the correlation value related to other variables. So it can be concluded that the model is said to have a good discriminant validity value.

B. Reliability Test

The reliability test determines the stability level of the meter (Wijaya, 2013). In this test, a reliability test was carried out using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability which can be called reliable if the values are ≥ 0.6 and ≥ 0.7 (Siswoyo, 2017). The results of the reliability test of this study met the requirements for Cronbach alpha ≥ 0.6 and composite reliability ≥ 0.7 presented in Table 8.

Table 8 Cronbach's Alpha Value and Composite Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Results
Training (X1)	0.918	0.934	Reliable
Compensation (X2)	0.892	0.915	Reliable
Career Development (X3)	0.816	0.867	Reliable
Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.918	0.931	Reliable
SustainableEmployee Performance (Y2)	0.936	0.947	Reliable

Table 8. shows that all variables have a value of Cronbach's alpha > 0.6 and composite reliability > 0.7 . From this, it can be explained that all variables have good reliability and meet the requirements for Cronbach's alpha ≥ 0.6 and composite reliability ≥ 0.7 .

C. Structural Model Test (Inner Model)

The structural model test aims to determine the strength of the relationship with latent variables. The steps

for structural testing (internal model) in this test are estimating the value of the path coefficient, estimating the coefficient of determination (R^2), measuring the effect size (f^2), and validating the entire model with the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) and predictive significance tests (Q^2). The main structure of testing the structural model of this study is described in Figure 2.

Fig 2 Main Construct of Structural Model Test (Inner Model)

➤ *The Coefficient of Determination (R²)*

Based on the test results using the SmartPLS software version 3.2.9, the R-value was obtained² which shows the level of determination of the independent variable on the dependent variable as can be seen in Table 11.

Table 9 R Square value (R²)

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.732	0.724
Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.716	0.705

Table 9 shows that Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1) has an R-value of ²0.732 > 0.50, then the model can be said to be moderate. The value of 0.732 indicates that 73.2% of Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1) can be explained by the variables Training (X1), Compensation (X2), and Career Development (X3), while the remaining 26.8% is explained by other variables outside the model. Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2) has an R value²0.716 > 0.50, then the model can be said to be moderate. The value of 0.716 indicates that 71.6% of the Sustainable Employee Performance variable (Y2) can be explained by the variables Training (X1), Compensation (X2), Career Development (X3), and Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1), while the remaining 28.4% is in another variable.

➤ *Predictive Relevance Test (Q²)*

The predictive significance test (Q²) serves to validate the model. Predictive Relevance (Q²) > 0 explains that the model has good predictive value, then the value of Predictive Relevance (Q²) < 0 means that the model has no predictive value (Ghozali, 2015). The predictive importance (Q²) calculation results for this test are as follows:

- $Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R_{21})(1 - R_{22})$
- $Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0.732)(1 - 0.716)$
- $Q^2 = 1 - (0.268)(0.284)$
- $Q^2 = 1 - 0.076$
- $Q^2 = 0.924$

➤ *Information:*

- R²1 = R² Value of Employee Job Satisfaction
- R²2 = Sustainable Employee Performance R² Value

The results of predictive relevance (Q²) calculations produce a value of 0.924. This means that this test has good predictive relevance (0.924 > 0). The predictive relevance (Q²) value also shows that the exogenous latent variable as an explanatory variable is capable of predicting its endogenous performance, namely Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2).

➤ *Goodness of Fit (GoF) test*

This test is to validate the combined measurement model and structural model. The GoF assessment criteria are 0.1 = Small GoF, 0.25 = Moderate GoF, and 0.36 = Large GoF (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). The results of calculating the Index of Fit (GoF) in this test are as follows:

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0,6 \times 0,724}$$

$$GoF = 0.658\sqrt{0,434}$$

➤ *Information:*

- $AVE = (0.553+0.522+0.693+0.642+0.590) / 5 = 0.6$
- $R^2 = (0.732+0.716) / 2 = 0.724$

The results of the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) test yielded a value of 0.658. This means that the performance of the combined measurement model (outer model) and structural model (inner model) in this study is included in the GoF Large category (0.658 > 0.36).

➤ *Effect Size Test (f square)*

Effect size (f2) is measured to measure the goodness of the model or the magnitude of the influence of exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables. The effect size (f2) value of 0.02 is a small effect, 0.15 is a moderate effect, and 0.35 is a large effect at the structural level (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). Based on the results of calculations using the SmartPLS software version 3.2.9, the effect size (f2) is obtained which can be seen in Table 10.

Table 10 Effect Size Value (f2)

Variable	f square (f2)	Results
Training (X1)→Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.115	Intermediate
Training (X1)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.319	Big
Compensation (X2)→Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.097	Small
Compensation (X2)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.008	Small
Career Development (X3)→Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.170	Intermediate
Career Development (X3)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.027	Small
Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.133	Intermediate

D. *Hypothesis Testing*

This test is used to test whether or not there is an influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. Hypothesis testing between constructs was carried out using the bootstrapping calculation method with a significance level of 5% using SmartPLS 3.2.9. In calculating the hypothesis test, it can be seen from the Path Coefficient value, namely the T-statistic value of the relationship between variables in the study. In the comparison between the T-statistic test values using SamatPLS and the values in the T table using the formula $df = n - k$, $df = 103-5 = 98$. In the statistical table with a significance level (α) of 0.05, a T value can be obtained

table of 1.66055. Through the P-value, T arithmetic, and T table the following decisions can be made:

- $P-values > 0.05$ or $Tcount < ttable$, H_0 is accepted and H_1 is rejected.
- $P-values < 0.05$ or $T count > t table$, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.

The results of the calculation of hypothesis testing using SmartPLS 3.2.9. presented in Figure 3 and Table 11 below.

Fig 3 Testing Path Coefficient

Table 11 Partial Effect of Independent Variable on Dependent

Variable	Coefficient	T statistics	P-values	Results
Direct Influence				
Training (X1)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.281	2,552	0.011	Significant positive influence
Compensation (X2)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.244	3,032	0.003	Significant positive influence
Career Development (X3)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.420	3,428	0.001	Significant positive influence
Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.186	1,253	0.211	No effect and no significant
Training (X1)→Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.375	3,412	0.001	Significant positive influence
Compensation (X2)→Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	-0.088	0.872	0.384	No effect and no significant
Career Development (X3)→Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.442	5,150	0.000	Significant positive influence
Indirect Influence				
Training (X1)→Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.092	2,282	0.011	Significant positive influence
Compensation (X2)→Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.106	2,095	0.018	Significant positive influence
Career Development (X3)→Employee Job Satisfaction (Y1)→ Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.157	2,290	0.011	Significant positive influence

➤ *The Discussion of this Research is:*

- Training has a positive and significant effect on sustainable personnel performance. The results of this study are reinforced by the theory of T. Ramayah & Juhari Noor Faezah & Zikri Muhammad (2019) that training of tangible and intangible employees by the management of an organization or company aims to motivate them to work harder and be successful. achieve organizational or corporate goals.
- Compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is to the research by Sari Dewi Oktari and Agatha Rinta Suhardi (2021) that employees or workers who enjoy their work speed up the completion of their work thereby increasing the performance of the employee or worker.
- Career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is by the research of Desi Permatasar and Yeki Candra (2020) that employees or workers enjoy their work and this speeds up their completion which ultimately improves the performance of these employees or workers.
- Job satisfaction has no effect and is not related to employee performance. The results of this study are reinforced by the theory A Hadi Arifin & Faisal Matriadi (2022), that someone with high job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards his job.
- Training has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction. The results of this study are supported by Iskandar's theory (2018) which emphasizes that the interests of employees and the organization or company must be integrated to satisfy the desires of employees while at the same time achieving organizational or company goals. to achieve.

- Compensation does not affect job satisfaction and is not important. This is to Pramono's research (2020) which found that work stress, conflict, job satisfaction, and rewards have a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction.
- Career development has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This is by research conducted by Handoko and Nawawi (Dr. Muhammad Busro, 2018) that career development has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction.
- Employee job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect as a mediator of continuous job training. The results of this study are in line with Iskandar's research (2018) that training is mediated by job satisfaction and has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
- Employee job satisfaction as a rewarding agent has a positive and significant effect on advanced employee performance. The results of this study are in line with McHugh (2017) that compensation has a positive and significant effect on advanced employee performance.
- Job satisfaction as a career development mediator has a positive and significant effect on advanced employee performance. The results of this study are in line with Ezeanyim & Ufoaroh (2019) that career development has a positive and significant effect on sustainable employee performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

➤ *Conclusion*

Conclusion regarding the effect of training, compensation, and career development on sustainable employee performance with employee job satisfaction as a mediating variable, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Training on Sustainable Employee Performance at Prolindo Group. Training Variables affect Sustainable Employee Performance, especially in indicators with the highest factor loading values, namely, Employees can apply training so that it is easy to understand to realize Sustainable Employee Performance.
- Compensation for Sustainable Employee Performance in Prolindo Group. The Compensation Variable affects Sustainable Employee Performance, especially on indicators with the highest factor loading values, namely companies providing outing or outbound town facilities to employees so that they can realize Sustainable Employee Performance.
- Career Development on Sustainable Employee Performance at Prolindo Group. The Career Development Variable influences Continuing Employee Performance, especially in indicators with the highest factor loading values, namely employees improving work systems and processes in an organization or activity.
- Employee Job Satisfaction on Sustainable Employee Performance in Prolindo Group. Employee Job Satisfaction Variable has no significant effect on Continuing Employee Performance, especially on indicators with the highest factor loading values, namely, employees are given salaries or wages according to what employees expect.

➤ Suggestion

As material for consideration with the hope of providing constructive improvements for the company is as follows:

- *Managerial Advice*
- ✓ Companies must be more consistent in carrying out training by providing training that meets the qualifications so that they can apply the training that is easy to understand.
- ✓ In terms of providing compensation to employees, it can be done by carrying out continuous supervision which at the same time provides a sense of security to employees both when they are inside and outside the office.
- ✓ In terms of providing compensation to employees, it can be done by carrying out continuous supervision which at the same time provides a sense of security to employees both when they are inside and outside the office.
- ✓ From the point of view of providing employee job satisfaction, this is done by being given a salary according to what employees expect.

• *Suggestions for Further Research*

This study has limitations in the implementation of data collection because this research was conducted. This study has limitations in the data collection process. The activeness of the respondents often made the respondents unable to concentrate on answering the questions posed by the researchers when distributing the questionnaires.

Therefore it becomes an obstacle in the information process for respondents before filling out the questionnaire so that the intent and purpose of this research cannot be captured clearly. In addition, the respondents of this study, amounting to 103 employees whose work placements were at the head office, were expected to touch employees whose work placements were located at office sites.

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